

PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN ENTERPRISES AND ORGANIZATIONS**Shadiyev Alisher Xudoynazarovich**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13729969>

Abstract. This article talks about the changes in the principles of labor resources management, orientation to the implementation of the motivation policy, which is important in modern conditions, as well as the personnel management system and principles.

Key words: Labor resources, management principles, changes, modern conditions, important, motivation policy, personnel management system, personnel management principles.

СИСТЕМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛОМ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ И В ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ

Аннотация. В статье говорится об изменении принципов управления трудовыми ресурсами, ориентации на реализацию мотивационной политики, что актуально в современных условиях, а также о системе и принципах управления персоналом.

Ключевые слова: Трудовые ресурсы, принципы управления, изменения, современные условия, важно, мотивационная политика, система управления персоналом, принципы управления персоналом.

INTRODUCTION

Economic reforms in Uzbekistan are shaping market relations and fundamentally changing the position of organizations. The existence of enterprises with different properties, sizes and activities leads to the formation of new economic and legal relations. This situation has an effect on the relations between people, their view of property, the obtained result and its efficiency is changing fundamentally. Since the main object of management is employees, in the process of managing a modern organization, the main attention is paid to the activities of employees, their mutual relations, interests, and ways to achieve goals.

One of the main goals of the adoption of the strategy of forming a socially oriented market economy in our republic is to improve the life of the population, including the employees of enterprises, to raise living and working conditions to a high level. At the enterprise level, regardless of the form of the property and the attitude towards it, it is important to rationally organize the management system of employees in order for employees to work effectively and to use their physical and mental potential to the fullest and to achieve the goals set for each organization. .

Due to the fact that the Republic of Uzbekistan is closely connected to the world economic system and is gradually transitioning to a market economy, new ownership enterprises, companies, firms, and societies are being formed at the scale of the national economy. The need to learn is ever increasing.

In today's practice, there are two different approaches to the problem of the employee and his management:

- human resources management;
- personnel management.

The concept of "human resource management" includes strategic aspects of management, as well as issues of social development, and they are given priority.

The concept of "employee management" means to work quickly with more personnel. If the first approach comes from the tasks of employment and its coordination at the state level, the second approach comes directly from the labor relations at the enterprise level and their coordination.

Personnel management means a system of interrelated organizational, economic and social activities aimed at developing the potential of people employed in the enterprise and using it effectively, creating the necessary conditions for their normal (moderate) activity. understood.

Such management is divided into functional and organizational management.

Functional management refers to issues directly related to personnel issues, i.e. personnel selection, dismissal, training, salary, etc. The concept of organizational management includes all persons and institutions directly responsible for personnel work, i.e. leaders, personnel department, trade unions, etc. Depending on the distribution of labor resources, the potential of human resources as development factors can be large or small. Approaching the issue in this way makes it possible to study and determine the labor potential of the society, the region, and enterprises.

Labor potential can be defined as labor resources in the qualitative dimension. It is clear from the above that the concept of "labor potential" is a special factor that helps to study the interaction of labor resources and the economy.

Management of a single complex system of human resources in an enterprise constitutes a single complex system. This system socially modifies his behavior by setting specific and selective goals. This has a very significant impact on management. At the same time, clearly well-chosen methods of influence are associated with investments made. Therefore, in many companies, human resource management is considered as the main strategy in the development of many companies.

Personnel management system means a system of interconnected economic, organizational and social activities aimed at developing the potential of people employed in the enterprise and

using it effectively, creating the necessary conditions for their normal activity. It is worth noting that a clear and conveniently designed system plays a very important role in increasing the efficiency of the enterprise. In systemized enterprises, it is distinguished by the ease of working with employees, that is, the control over assigned tasks is carried out correctly, and the process of information exchange is easy.

Personnel management is based on two groups of principles. Each principle serves to improve one or another aspect of personnel management. For example, the principle of progress answers the question of whether the management system within the enterprise is compatible with the management system of foreign or domestic advanced enterprises, meets the requirements of the times, and the principle of parallelism increases the speed of personnel management, etc.

Personnel management is based on the following rules:

1. Ensuring the integral connection of personnel planning with the company's development strategy.
2. Quantitative assessment of personnel costs and its impact on production economic indicators.
3. To determine the necessary competencies for effective work in the labor market.

All employees employed in the enterprise consist of two categories: producers or service providers and managers (leaders, specialist managers).

The efficiency of the work in the organization means the development of the vertical division of labor. It is about organizing the work of the manager to coordinate the activities of departments and workers.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that the innovative description of production, its high level of scientific capacity, the importance of product quality issues, changed the demand for employees, increased the importance of creative attitude to work and high professional skills. This required a fundamental change in social and spiritual issues, methods and principles of personnel management.

Changes in the principles of management of labor resources are aimed at the implementation of the motivation policy, which is important in modern conditions. In this process, the motivation policy is aimed at the development of collective forms of ownership (joint-stock and partnership companies, cooperatives), the involvement of employees in management, and the expansion of cooperation between the administration and employees in order to achieve common goals. This, in turn, encourages employees to develop their potential abilities, to work intensively and productively, and to have a creative attitude to work. The process of personnel management

shows that the main goal of the work is to plan employees and create favorable conditions for their activities.

REFERENCES

1. Shamsiya, A. (2023). HR MANAGEMENT AND COACHING IN THE INNOVATIVE ECONOMY AS A METHOD OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 712-717.
2. Abidovna, A. S. (2024). The Importance of Personnel Management in the Operations of an Organization. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 49, 971-975.
3. Alimova, S. O. FEATURES OF THE STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES. Kielce: Laboratorium Wiedzy Artur Borcuch.
4. Рахматов, Ж. А., Алимова, Ш. А., & Бобомуродов, К. Х. (2021). Стратегия инвестиционной политики Республики Узбекистан.
5. Алимова, Ш. А. (2021). ЦИФРОВАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК НОВЫЙ ЭТАП ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ И РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ, 234-238.
6. Alimova, S. (2024). NEW APPROACHES TO THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERACTION BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION AND EMPLOYERS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(7), 211-218.
7. Abidovna, A. S. (2024). COMMUNICATION PROCESS MANAGEMENT AS A TOOL TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF MODERN ORGANIZATIONS. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 49, 211-217.
8. Bazarova, M. (2024). MARKETING MANAGEMENT STRATEGY'S IMPORTANCE AND MODERN CONCEPT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
9. Bazarova, M. (2024). FEATURES OF BANKING MANAGEMENT IN THE ACTIVITIES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
10. Хайитов, Ш. Н., & Базарова, М. С. (2020). Роль иностранных инвестиций в развитии экономики Республики Узбекистан. In *Современные проблемы социально-экономических систем в условиях глобализации* (pp. 284-287).
11. Базарова, М. С., & Пулатов, Ш. Ш. (2019). Проблемы банковской системы узбекистана и пути их решения. *Современные проблемы социально-экономических систем в условиях глобализации*, 131-133.
12. Bazarova, M. S. (2022). FACTORS THAT ENSURE THE SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION OF A SYSTEM OF KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS IN

- THE FIELD OF HIGHER EDUCATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 582-586.
13. Базарова, М. С. (2021). ЭКОНОМИКА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН И РОЛЬ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ИНВЕСТИЦИЙ В ЕЁ РАЗВИТИИ. In *Современные проблемы социально-экономических систем в условиях глобализации* (pp. 350-354).
 14. Khudoynazarovich, S. A. (2023). CREATING VALUE IN A TOURIST DESTINATION.
 15. Xudoynazarovich, S. A. (2024). KORXONA VA TASHKIOTLARDA PERSONALNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMI VA TAMOYILLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 48, 685-690.
 16. Shadiyev, A. (2024). TA'LIM MENEJMENTI. TA'LIMNI BOSHQARISH USULLARI VA QARORLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
 17. Khudoynazarovich, S. A. (2021). An Opportunity of Internet Marketing in Tourism Sphere. *International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development*, 3(3), 356-361.
 18. Shadiyev, A. (2022). EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SINGAPORE TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 23(23).
 19. Ibodulloyevich, I. E. (2024). XIZMATLAR SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI.
 20. Ibodulloyevich, I. E. (2024). XIZMATLAR SIFATI VA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.
 21. Ibodulloyevich, I. E. (2024). Ijtimoiy Soliq Stavkasini Kamaytirish Orqali Davlat Budjeti Daromatlarini Oshirish Imkoniyatlari. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 48, 348-353.
 22. Ikromov, E. (2024). SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 103-109.
 23. Ikromov, E. (2024). FEATURES AND ADVANTAGES OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 98-102.
 24. Khalilov, B. B. (2024). INTERNATIONAL ACCOUNTING ANALYSIS. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 48, 740-745.
 25. Халилов, Б. Б., & Курбанов, Ф. Г. (2020). Важность подготовки кадров в экономике. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (6 (90)), 12-14.
 26. Khalilov, B. B. (2024). ROLE OF INTERNAL AUDITING IN INTERNATIONAL COMPANIES. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 47, 413-419.

27. Bakhodirovich, K. B. (2023). CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING ACCOUNTING IN SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP. IMRAS, 6(6), 161-165.
28. Bahodirovich, K. B. (2023). The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) Mean to Businesses and Investors in Uzbekistan. Miasto Przyszłości, 42, 746-750.
29. Nafisa, R. (2024). THE PLACE AND ROLE OF TOURISM IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 48, 279-284.
30. Mukhammedrizaevna, T. M., Bakhridinovna, A. N., & Olimovna, R. N. TOURIST LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: STRATEGIES FOR REDUCING COST AND IMPROVING SERVICE. Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych, 90.
31. кизи Рахмонкулова, Н. О. (2023). КИЧИК САНОАТ ЗОНАЛАРИНИНГ ҲУДУДЛАР ИҚТИСОДИЁТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДАГИ ЎРНИ. " Экономика и туризм" международный научно-инновационной журнал, 6(14).
32. Орипов, М. А., Аминова, Н. Б., & Рахманкулова, Н. О. (2020). Экологически чистое и устойчивое управление цепочками поставок в экономике платформы. Вестник науки и образования, (13-2 (91)), 28-30.
33. Bakhridinovna, A. N., & Kizi, R. N. O. (2021). The impact of the digital economy on resource consumption.
34. Nafisa, R. (2024). THE ROLE OF THE MODERN MANAGER IN THE ECONOMY. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 49, 148-154.
35. Raxmonqulova, N. (2023). THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRYPTOCURRENCIES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 192-194.
36. Ruzmetov, B., Jumaeva, Z. K., & Xudayarova, M. (2021). International experience in attracting foreign direct investment. International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development, 3(4), 38-43.
37. ЖУМАЕВА, З. СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ТОЧЕК ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОГО РОСТА В БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. ЭКОНОМИКА, 4, 455-458.
38. Жумаева, З. К. (2023). Потенциал инвестиционной стратегии развития региона. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 41, 333-337.
39. Jumayeva, Z. (2024). THE NEED FOR AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH IN MANAGING ORGANIZATIONS. Modern Science and Research, 3(1), 557-562.

40. Ruzmetov, B., Ruzmetov, S., Bakhtiyarov, S., Dzhumaeva, Z., & Juraev, K. (2023). Formation of supporting points for production growth based on diversification of the regional industry. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 449, p. 01001). EDP Sciences.
41. Jumayeva, Z. Q. (2024). METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMS OF THE REGION BASED ON THE ACTIVATION OF INVESTMENT PROCESSES. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 4(7), 137-140.
42. Hakimovich, T. M. (2024). IQDISODIY NOCHOR KORXONALARNI MOLIYAVIY SOGLOMLASHTIRISHNING MOLIYA-KREDIT MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.
43. Hakimovich, T. M. (2024). KORPORATIV KORXONALARDA ISH O'RINLARINI YARATISH VA BANDLIKNI TA'MINLASHNING SAMARALI USULLARI.
44. Hakimovich, T. M. (2024). MINTAQALARDA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI RIVOJLANISHIGA INVESTITSIYA JALB QILISH.
45. Hakimovich, T. M. (2024). ZAMONAVIY MENEJMENT YONDASHUVLARI ASOSIDA XALQ TA'LIMI TIZIMINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.
46. Hakimovich, T. M. (2024). XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASI RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI VA TAMOYILLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 48, 341-347.
47. Toshov, M. (2024). IMPROVING PUBLIC EDUCATION SYSTEM MANAGEMENT BASED ON MODERN MANAGEMENT APPROACHES. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6), 716-722.
48. Toshov, M. (2024). WAYS TO DEVELOP AGROTOURISM AND ITS INFRASTRUCTURE IN POST-PANDEMIC CONDITIONS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6), 723-729.
49. Toshov, M. (2024). EFFECTIVE METHODS OF CREATING JOBS AND PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT IN CORPORATE ENTERPRISES. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6), 710-715.
50. Toshov, M. (2024). ATTRACTING INVESTMENT TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF BUSINESS ACTIVITIES IN THE REGIONS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6), 696-702.
51. Sodiqova, N. (2024). THE MAIN STAGES OF THE INNOVATION PROCESS IN THE ENTERPRISE AND ITS MANAGEMENT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6), 703-709.

52. Sodiqova, N. (2024). MANAGEMENT OF INNOVATIONS IN ENTERPRISE ACTIVITY OPPORTUNITIES TO USE FOREIGN EXPERIENCE. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6), 688-695.
53. Sodiqova, N. (2024). THE MAIN METHODS OF SELECTING INNOVATIVE PROJECTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6), 682-687.
54. Turayevna, S. N. (2024). THE ESSENCE AND CONTENT OF THE CONCEPT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION IN BUSINESS MANAGEMENT. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 48, 554-558.
55. Sodiqova, N. (2024). KORXONALARDA INNOVATSION LOYIHALARNI BAHOLASH TARTIBI VA TANLASH USULLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
56. Sodiqova, N. (2024). KORXONADA INNOVATSIYANING MOHIYATI VA UNING ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
57. To'rayevna, S. N. (2024). YANGI IQTISODIYOT VA UNING MOLIYA BOZORLARIGA TA'SIRI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, (45), 333-339.
58. Turayevna, S. N. (2024). THE EFFECT OF LABOR PROMOTION ON WORK EFFICIENCY. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 49, 142-147.
59. Bustonovna, D. Z. (2024). CREATIVE THINKING AND ITS APPLICATION IN ECONOMICS.[Data set]. Zenodo.
60. Bostonovna, D. Z. (2023). CONCEPTUAL BASIS OF IMPROVEMENT OF BANK AUDIT IN COMMERCIAL BANKS. *IMRAS*, 6(6), 118-124.
61. Bostonovna, D. Z. (2023). USE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. *International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers*, 11(9), 607-613.
62. Bostonovna, D. Z. (2023). WAYS OF USING REENGINEERING IN ENTERPRISES. *International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers*, 11(7), 430-435.
63. Bostonovna, D. Z. (2023). CONCEPTUAL BASIS OF IMPROVEMENT OF BANK AUDIT IN COMMERCIAL BANKS. *IMRAS*, 6(6), 118-124.
64. Jumayeva, Z. (2024). ROLE OF THE STATE IN REGULATING THE ECONOMY. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 511-516.
65. Akbarovna, N. N. (2024). XIZMAT KO 'RSATISH SOHASINING TASNIFIY BELGILARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 48, 357-364.

66. Akbarovna, N. N. (2024). OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRYPTOCURRENCIES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, (45), 320-326.
67. Akbarovna, N. N. (2024). XIZMAT KO 'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY RESURSLARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA KO 'RSATKICHLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 46, 326-335.
68. Naimova, N. (2024). STRATEGY OF DIGITALIZATION OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES OF THE STATE TAX COMMITTEE. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 635-641.
69. Akbarovna, N. N. (2024). KORXONADA MEHNAT FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISHNING MOHIYATI VA ASOSLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 49, 133-141.
70. Akbarovna, N. N. (2023). RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA MOLIYA VA MOLIYAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARNING ORNI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 41, 446-449.
71. Naimova, N. (2024). DIGITALIZATION IN OUR COUNTRY'S EDUCATION SYSTEM AND APPLICATION IN THE DIGITAL WORLD. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 912-917.
72. Mahmudovna, Q. G. (2024). RAQOBAT STRATEGIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA RAQOBATNI BAHOLASH USULLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 48, 715-720.
73. Mahmudovna, Q. G. (2024). Oliy ta'lim muassasalari raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda innovatsion faoliyatning ahamiyati.
74. Mahmudovna, Q. G. (2024). Oliy ta'lim muassasalari raqobatbardoshligini tavsiflovchi omillar. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 46, 620-627.
75. Mahmudovna, G. G. (2024). Competitive strategies, the importance of using innovation in their implementation. *Iqtisodiyot va zamonaviy texnologiya jurnali| journal of economy and modern technology*, 3(5), 8-14.
76. Mahmudovna, Q. G. (2024). Raqobat strategiyalari, ularni amalga oshirishda innovatsiyalardan foydalanishning ahamiyati. *Iqtisodiyot va zamonaviy texnologiya jurnali| journal of economy and modern technology*, 3(5), 15-21.